

THE USE OF MODERN TEACHING METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING "CONCERTMASTER SKILLS"

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The subject "Concertmaster skills" at the Music Academic Lyceum aims to prepare students of piano departments for independent work as concertmasters. During the training, students should get acquainted with the best examples of folk art, vocal and instrumental music; gain skills and abilities to accompany soloists, have an idea of the range, tessitura of vocal voices and instruments of a symphony orchestra, their specific features; read from a sheet and transpose simple works. To solve these problems, it will be useful to use modern teaching methods.

Multi-level training: taking into account the individual characteristics of each student, that is, a differentiated approach to each student, taking into account his specific knowledge, skills and abilities; necessary in order to give each student a chance to develop their potential abilities.

This method is recommended to be used at the stage of drawing up individual curricula of students: the selection of works should be made taking into account:

- a). technical training;
- b). musical and emotional preparation;
- c). the ability to read from a sheet;
- d). the ability to transpose;
- e). general intellectual development.

For example, according to the requirements of the first semester, the performance of arias by an ancient composer (Bach, Handel, Scarlatti, Haydn, Mozart) and romances by foreign authors (Mozart, Schubert, Schumann, Weckerlen) is provided for 9th grade students.

Student "A" (high technical training, musicality, developed outlook, diligence):

G.Handel – Aria of Rodelinda

F.Schubert – "Trout", "Barcarola".

Student "B" (average technical training, high emotionality, poor reading skills):

G.Handel – Aria of Almira

F. Schubert – "To music", "You are my peace".

Programmed learning: B.Skinner's method consists in improving the effective assimilation of material constructed in the form of a consistent presentation of

information with mandatory control of its assimilation (a system of small "steps").

Basic requirements and principles:

- a). small parts of tasks (portions) that do not require much effort from students to master them;
- b). low difficulty level of each portion of the material (for positive reinforcement);
- c). individualization of the pace of learning (each student works at an optimal pace for himself);
- d). a uniform course of study for all students – there are no attempts at a differentiated approach, as in the previous method.

All the difference between students will be expressed only in the duration of the study of the work.

This method is recommended to be used if it is necessary to study a certain work by all students: for example, A.Dargomyzhsky's romance "Night zefir" as a competitive compulsory work for 8th grade students.

Student "A" (high technical training, sound proficiency, broad horizons): we will divide this work into three portions (in accordance with the form of the romance – rondo AVASA), studying parts A, B and C sequentially in three lessons. Then, in two lessons, we will combine them into a single whole, building a dynamic and semantic culmination.

Student "B" (poor technical training, lack of sound control, inattention, but the desire to participate in the competition and succeed): we will divide the romance into six portions, studying parts A, B and C. In six lessons, then we will combine it into a single whole in four lessons.

Role-playing game: (the method of Elkonin, Leontiev, Vygotsky).

It is recommended to use it at the final stage of the study of the work.

Components of the method:

- a). the student presents himself in the place of the composer of the work (style, epoch, task, to whom he addresses);
- b). the student presents himself in the place of the soloist-vocalist (how best to show his voice, his musicality, technical and semantic climaxes);
- c). the student presents himself in place the listener (what he wants to hear in this romance);
- d). Finally, the student presents himself as an accompanist (here it is recommended to use the "Fish-memo" method with two fins):

- 1) what the concertmaster needs to know:

musical and poetic text,
rubato of the soloist,
timbre and strength of the voice
2) what will happen if you don't know it:
possible breakdown, stop,
discrepancy in tempo,
drowning of the soloist

This method makes it possible to recreate the structure and functional links of the future professional activity of students (accompanist, concertmaster) in a playful educational manner, and also brings the situation of the educational process closer to real conditions, generating the need for knowledge and their practical application.

Problem-based learning: creating problematic situations by a teacher in order to solve non-standard tasks using non-standard methods.

It is recommended to use it at the final stage of learning the piece (during rehearsal with the soloist).

The student should know that in the process of performing the accompaniment, he completely depends on the soloist and in case of some kind of failure in the performance of the latter ("forgot the text", "forgot the words", "got up earlier or later", "missed a few bars", "unclean intonation", etc.) should immediately react to this ("pick up the soloist", suggest the text of the words, play along with the soloist's part). It is useful for a teacher to create such situations during the rehearsal. Purpose: to activate the student's attention.

The domino method is also useful in this context: we mentally cut the piece into pieces and verbally build their place in the overall structure, which helps a lot to "pick up" the soloist if he stumbled or missed a few bars.

The use of these methods will allow the teacher to successfully cope with the tasks assigned to him.

